

**THEORETICAL ASPECT OF DEVELOPMENT OF CULTURE OF
INTERETHNIC COMMUNICATION AMONG STUDENTS**

Makhmudova Muyassar Makhmudovna

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, department
of innovative educational technologies
and pedagogy, professor, SamSIFL.

Nargiza Karimova Mamatkadyrovna

Assistant teacher,
department of innovative educational technologies and
pedagogy, SamSIFL.

Annotation: This article describes the process of formation of the culture of interethnic communication as a long-term, multifaceted process and is associated with the emergence of a culture of human relations. The article also addresses issues and recommendations for fostering interethnic tolerance.

Keywords: behavior, communication, humanity, social, mechanism, interpersonal, dignity, factors.

Communication is as important to us as air in interpersonal relationships. Preparing the youth of our republic for a new social environment, educating them in the spirit of the times is one of the urgent and priority tasks of this day. The fate of the reforms implemented in our Republic depends on the moral image and personal integrity of the youth. The realization of these tasks requires a conscious inculcation of democratic principles in human relations.

Education is an important tool that helps every person to understand the world. In the process of education, the person is social, cultural, economic. enters into political relations. He will have the opportunity to enrich his political and cultural level. The essence of this approach is manifested in the development of cultural literacy of a person. This is one of the tools for measuring the result of education, and in this process

it is necessary to be based on the following directions and mechanisms of cultural literacy: the formation of a conscious point of view in relation to existence; to realize the impossibility of perceiving the world uniformly; understand and respect the culture of other peoples; covers issues such as awareness of choice.

Formation of the culture of inter-ethnic communication in students should be based on intellectual understanding of the culture of other nations. Only then students will have the opportunity to understand the unique internal aspects of the culture of representatives of other nations. At the same time, students are taught tolerance, other . it is necessary to educate in the spirit of positive attitude towards the representatives of the nation. Students should be able to internalize the moral views and customs of representatives of other nations and make it a part of their life. In order to have a deep understanding of the culture of other peoples, it is not enough to admire it and have complete information about it. The ability of students to have inter-ethnic communication indicates their ability to perceive the uniqueness of other peoples. To achieve such a result, it is necessary to identify the specific components of having inter-ethnic communication. They include:

- recognition of specific aspects of important value directions;

- to perceive the language of other nations as the uniqueness of human thinking and its form of existence;

- adopting a style of communication that embodies a certain national culture;

- to naturally respect the moral views, customs, traditions, ceremonies of other nations;

- to be able to accept the mentality and uniqueness of national character of other peoples.

Our analysis showed that until today, the structure and criteria of the process of teaching interethnic communication in all works aimed at the formation of interethnic communication among students. the age characteristics of the students were not taken into account enough.

As a result of the analysis of works aimed at the formation of interethnic communication among students, we tried to describe this phenomenon. Under the concept of international communication is understood the combined set of many knowledges and strong beliefs. In this case, their actions and situations should be mutually compatible. On the basis of this, open interpersonal communication, cooperation and various relationships are formed. An environment of tolerance and cooperation is created in the society on the basis of mutual understanding of different nationalities.

Instilling the culture of inter-ethnic communication into the minds of students takes into account many factors and conditions, inter-ethnic relations occupy a special place in their development. These factors and conditions can speed up the pedagogical process aimed at this goal or slow down its progress.

Interethnic communication should appear as a component of individual culture.

Personal culture is a concept that refers to the complex of material and spiritual wealth created by the mind and hands of a specific individual, and the actions related to his humanity and compliance with spiritual and moral requirements during his life. A person's culture is manifested in his adherence to creative ideas, national culture, spiritual and moral values. A person's culture is a criterion that determines the level of his spiritual education.

The signs of personal culture are also expressed by a person's acquisition of the following spiritual and moral qualities, human relations, virtues: being faithful, conscientious, religious and religious, polite and disciplined, not being late for studies and work without reason, striving to enrich knowledge and worldview, keeping promises, not to harm people. to do good and not be grateful for it, to respect the elders and to honor the little ones, to show respect to the elderly, women and children, to be kind and warm to others, to be humble, not to call others names, not to laugh at the shortcomings of people, not to mock them. not discriminating against the weak, not interfering with the work and rest of the people around, hospitality, paying attention to one's inner and outer world, observing speech culture, preserving public property,

physical and spiritual cleanliness, etc. Personal culture unites him with the team, gives him the opportunity to make many friends. In order for personal culture to be perfect, every person should enrich his spiritual and moral qualities, educate himself, control and manage himself, be able to have a critical attitude, expand his worldview and raise his level.

It is known that personal culture is a large-scale phenomenon, and we tried to analyze only its directions related to the development of the culture of interethnic communication among students. A person has specific characteristics as a member of a certain society, a representative of a nation. He enters into social relations in the process of learning, communicating with others and performing certain activities. The formation of the personality takes place in a consistent process that takes place step by step. At certain stages of its development, a person acquires originality and elegance. One of these stages corresponds to adolescence. This period occupies a special place in the formation of human personality. Adolescence is a very complex and conflicting period. Because this period is the stage of active formation of the personality. At the same time, this is a very responsible period, and at this stage of a person's life, the foundations of morality, social rules, attitude towards oneself, surrounding people and society are formed. At this age, individual aspects of human character and interpersonal relationships are stabilized. The main guiding aspect of this period is manifested in a person's desire for personal improvement. This is reflected in his self-awareness, expression and affirmation of his personality. During this period, the development of cognitive activity of students will be ready to implement all methods of mental activity performed by adults. During this period, cognitive processes are as refined and flexible as possible. As a result, students' attitude towards people around them changes. New ways of communication appear in them, their demands on their intelligence increase. They now begin to think logically, interpret events theoretically and analyze their own activities. At the same time, they should be encouraged to think and think about moral, spiritual and political issues. They should get used to analyzing the hypotheses put forward and drawing conclusions. As a result of the deepening of their knowledge

about themselves, the surrounding people, all members of the society, they begin to understand their identity more deeply. As a result, students feel inclined towards the main types of activities. As a result of studying, studying, working, establishing communication, students are able to think about the content, goals and tasks of their activities. During this period, the process of self-control accelerates. As a result, they have an increased desire to manage themselves and plan their activities.

Based on one's life goal, achieving the goals set for oneself is related to the formation of willpower in students. For example, self-management, coordination of abilities, ability to cope with a large amount of load in order to manage activities, on the basis of this, one strives to achieve high results in one's activities. In the process of such development, the value system of students is formed. This, in turn, makes it possible to determine the content of the student's activity. It is reflected in students' communication, choice-based attitude towards others, their assessment and self-evaluation. At the same time, the cultural equality of the individual begins to form. In this way, the students have the experience of their own cultural affiliation and a positive attitude towards other cultures. It is these students who have an understanding of social roles, interest in communicating within a micro-society, the need for mutual recognition and understanding of the people around them, which lead to encounters with other cultures. From this period, students develop social behavior skills necessary for their future life. In addition, the ability to interact, social restraint, positive or negative attitudes towards the surrounding people are manifested. An important sign of this period is that students have personal positions and perspectives. As a result, they have a high level of interest in themselves, a desire to understand their inner world, and the development of theoretical analysis skills.

Based on the above-mentioned points, it can be said that the period of adolescence is extremely favorable for the formation of communicative skills and provides an opportunity for students to develop high-level interpersonal and inter-ethnic relations.

REFERENCES

1. Republic of Uzbekistan Presidential Decree No. PF-60 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", January 28, 2022
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education". - Collection of Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, September 23, 2020
3. Mamatkadirovna N. K. Pedagogical system of development of culture of international communication in students //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 11. – С. 245-247.
4. KARIMOVA N. PRINCIPLES TO DEVELOP THE LITERACY OF INTERNATIONAL COMMUNICATION CULTURE IN STUDENTS //ЎЗМУ ХАБАРЛАРИ ВЕСТНИК НУУЗ АСТА NUUZ. – 2022.
5. KARIMOVA N. MUTUAL-COLLECTIVE LEARNING //JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH. – 2021.
6. Mamatkadirovna K. N. JARAYONIDA TALABALARNING KOMMUNIKATIV FAOLIYATINI SHAKILLANTIRISHDA TA'LIM INFORMASION TEXNOLOGIYADAN FOYDALANISH //Ta'lim fidoyilari. – 2022. – Т. 18. – №. 5. – С. 338-341.
7. Mamatkadirovna N. K. Pedagogical system of development of culture of international communication in students //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 11. – С. 245-247.
8. Mamatkadirovna A. K. et al. Translation as a Special Type of Language and Intercultural Communication //JournalNX. – С. 176-180.
9. Karimova N. Professional and moral competence of primary school teachers: essence, structure, content //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. – 2019. – Т. 7. – №. 11.
10. Aminova FH Didactic basics of teaching students to create communication text. Ped.fan nomz.authorref. - T., 2007.- 23 p.
11. Andramonova I.M. Ethnology: Textbook. / I.M. Andramonova. - M.: Vldos-Press, 2002. - 192 p.